

e-ISSN: 3048-6025

Volume 04 Issue 02
Jul-Dec 2026

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Submission Date: Apr
06, 2026

Copyright Received
Date: Apr 15, 2026

Quercetin as Neuroprotective Agent: Mechanistic and Therapeutic Potential in Neurodegenerative Diseases

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ABSTRACT

Neurodegenerative diseases Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, Huntington's, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, lead to ongoing loss of neurons, cognitive decreased, movement problem, oxidative stress, and long-term inflammation in the brain. The increasing global impact of these diseases calls for effective prevention and treatment Quercetin is a natural flavonoid found in many fruits and vegetables, has shown potential as a neuroprotective because of its biological effects. It summarizes the pharmacological role, production, metabolism, and protective role of quercetin in relation to neurodegenerative diseases. Research from both in-vitro and in-vivo studies shows that quercetin has strong antioxidant effects. It works by decreasing reactive oxygen species, binding to metal ions, and boosting natural antioxidant enzymes, and oxidative stress. Quercetin also enhance neuroinflammation by blocking NF- κ B, MAPK, and STAT3 signaling, decreased microglial activation, and promote anti-inflammatory cytokines like IL-10. It impacts the buildup of harmful proteins, such as amyloid- β , tau, and α -synuclein increases breakdown via the ubiquitin-proteasome system and autophagy. Quercetin helps neurons survive by encouraging new nerve cell growth, increasing neurotrophic factors.

Keywords:- Quercetin, Neurodegenerative diseases, Oxidative stress, Neuroinflammation, Protein aggregation, Neuroprotection, Antioxidant activity, Neurotransmitter regulation

INTRODUCTION

Neuronal degeneration is a process that involves the loss of neurons in the brain and neuron system. This degradation often causes severe illnesses such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, and other neurological related disorders. As neuron degeneration occur, vital brain function become impaired, resulting in cognitive decline, motor dysfunction and body disability (1). Cognitive impairment is the progressive degradation of cognitive functions, such as memory, attention, language, and problem-solving ability. The buildup of aberrant proteins, such as tau tangles and beta-amyloid plaques, in Alzheimer's disease interferes with neuronal transmission and reduces cognitive performance (2). Similarly, Other neurodegenerative illnesses cause cognitive problems due to particular brain areas degenerating, such as Lewy body dementia and frontotemporal dementia (3). In Parkinson's disease, the degeneration of neurons that produce dopamine in the brain causes motor symptoms such as tremors, stiffness, bradykinesia (slowed movement), and postural instability (4). In contrast, ALS damages the motor neurons in the brain and spinal cord, causing stiffness, weakness, and ultimately paralysis in the muscles (5),(6).

The increasing prevalence of neurodegenerative diseases presents significant changes to healthcare(7),(8). The social impact of neurodegenerative diseases, including costs, lost productivity, and caregiver, underscores the urgent need for effective preventive strategies(9). Prevent for neurodegenerative diseases like lifestyle interventions, such as consistent physical activity, a balanced diet, mental stimulation, and social interaction, Which have been shown to improve brain function and lower the risk of cognitive function(10). Early detection and diagnosis of neurodegenerative diseases, coupled timely

medical interventions and targeted treatment can slow disease progression and improve result for affected individuals(11),(12).

QUERCETIN: AN OVERVIEW

Quercetin is a flavanol molecule is often found in fruits, vegetables, and plant-based beverages. Its chemical structure is a flavonoid with hydroxyl groups with potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Quercetin is exhibits low toxicity, its bioavailability and metabolism factors such as food matrix, gut health, and formulation(13,14). Quercetin discovered by Albert Szent-Györgyi in 1936 leading to the identification and classification of flavonoids. Quercetin's isolation paved the way for extensive research into its biological activities and medicinal applications. Its antioxidant properties, quercetin garnered attention for Potential in combating oxidative stress and protecting cells from damage(15). Quercetin's therapeutic potential expanded to include anti-inflammatory, antihypertensive, and anticancer effects, its incorporation into dietary supplements and functional foods (16–18) .

Properties, Structure, Production and Occurrence

Quercetin is a yellow crystalline solid characterized by bitter taste, possesses unique properties that it as a flavonoid group. It is not compatible with water solubility, but it is slightly soluble in alcohol and fully soluble in glacial acetic acid and alkaline liquids for solubility. Structurally, quercetin contain a common flavone, contain two benzene rings connected via heterocyclic pyrone ring. Its family of naturally occurring substances that is present only in plants. Quercetin, alongside over 2,000 other flavonoids, emerges as a product of condensation from p-glycosides. This compound find in various food items and

plants, including fruits, seeds, vegetables, tea, coffee, and natural dyes. Its primary source often involves the hydrolysis of rutin,

a flavonoid glycoside, although synthetic production methods also exist.

Fig.1:-Chemical structure of Quercetin.

Table 1:-Represents the amount of quercetin in food source.

Food source	Quercetin Content (per 100g)
Apples	4-30 mg
Onions	10-30 mg
Berries (e.g., blueberries)	3-13 mg
Citrus fruits (e.g., oranges)	2-10 mg
Leafy greens (e.g., spinach)	4-10 mg
Tomatoes	1-7 mg
Red grapes	1-6 mg
Red wine	1-5 mg
Tea	2-3 mg

Biosynthesis of quercetin:

Plants exploit the production of phytochemicals like flavonoids as a defensive strategy against external stresses[24]. In particular, flavonoids are essential for defending plants from UV radiation and lipid peroxidation. Research,

carried out by Mohle et al. In 1985, has shown that when dill cell cultures are exposed to UV-B radiation, quercetin-3-O-β-glucuronide, a kind of flavonoid, is mostly synthesized[25],[26]. This discovery implies that UV radiation strictly controls the manufacture of flavonoids. Quercetin and

other flavonoids are essentially produced by plants as a defensive mechanism against environmental stresses like UV radiation(19),(20).

Absorption, metabolism, distribution, and excretion processes play crucial roles in the fate of quercetin in the body:

Quercetin glycosides exhibit relatively low absorption rates in the small intestine. However, in the lower bowel, the microflora enzymatically hydrolyses these flavonoid-glycosides into quercetin and sugars. Subsequently, quercetin is absorbed into the enterohepatic system(21),(22). Upon oral administration of quercetin to rabbits or rats, studies have identified three main metabolites in the urine: 3,4 dihydroxyphenyl acetic acid, 3-methoxy-4-hydroxy phenylacetic acid (Hom vanillic acid), and m-hydroxy phenylacetic acid(23). These metabolites are believed to form in the liver through ring fusion. Additionally, when quercetin was administered to rats via intraperitoneal injection, the 3'-o-methyl-ether of quercetin (isorhamnetin) was identified as a metabolite in bile(24),(25).

Addressing the distribution, metabolism, and excretion of 4-[14C] quercetin in male ACI rats, it was shown that around 20% of the dosage was absorbed from the digestive system after oral administration (26). The absorbed quercetin was eliminated as glucuronide or sulphate conjugates in the bile and urine within 48 hours (27). Three hours after a single 2.3 mg/kg oral dosage of quercetin was given to rats, autoradiographic examination revealed that the majority of radioactivity stayed in the digestive system, with modest amounts found in the blood, liver, kidney, lung, and ribs(26),(28). In a research involving five human participants, no measurable quantities of quercetin were observed in the plasma or urine following oral administration of 4 grams of quercetin (29).

Quercetin's Molecular and Cellular Targets:

Quercetin is a flavonoid that has a wide range of biological action, including in regulating inflammation, oxidative stress, lifespan, and cell survival. Numerous signaling pathways, including as Nrf2/ARE, NF- κ B, MAPK, PI3K/Akt, and SIRT1 activation, are used to achieve its effects. A thorough explanation of these molecular targets is provided below(30).

The Nrf2/ARE Pathway (Antioxidant Response Regulation):

Nuclear Factor Erythroid 2-Related Factor 2 (Nrf2) and the Antioxidant Response Element (ARE), which controls the expression of cytoprotective and antioxidant genes, are the transcription factors that govern the Nrf2/ARE pathway, a critical cellular defense mechanism against oxidative stress that is essential for preserving cellular redox homeostasis and preventing oxidative damage(31),(32).

Mechanism of the Nrf2/ARE Pathway's Action: Normal cytoplasmic binding of Nrf2 to Kelch-like ECH-associated protein 1 (Keap1) promotes its ubiquitination and subsequent proteasome-mediated destruction. In the absence of oxidative stress, this stops the needless activation of antioxidant responses. Nevertheless, this Keap1-Nrf2 association can be broken by some substances, such as quercetin, which results in Nrf2 stabilization and nuclear translocation(33).

The Function of Quercetin in Nrf2 Activation: By altering the cysteine residues in Keap1, quercetin, a naturally occurring flavonoid, acts as an indirect antioxidant and stops Nrf2 from degrading. By preventing Keap1 from suppressing Nrf2, this alteration permits Nrf2 to build up and move into the nucleus(34).

Gene Activation and Nuclear Translocation: After entering the nucleus, Nrf2 attaches itself to ARE sequences found in the promoter regions of genes related to detoxification and antioxidant defense. Antioxidant proteins and phase II detoxification enzymes that combat oxidative stress and shield cellular constituents from harm are encoded by these genes(35),(33).

Important Target Genes That Nrf2 Activates:

NAD(P)H quinone oxidoreductase 1 (NQO1): Prevents oxidative stress and redox cycling by converting quinones into less hazardous hydroquinone's. Superoxide radicals are converted into oxygen and hydrogen peroxide by the enzyme superoxide dismutase (SOD)(36).

Glutathione S-transferases (gusts): Help detoxify by facilitating the conjugation of glutathione (GSH) with harmful electrophiles. Heme oxygenase-1 (HO-1): Provides cytoprotective and anti-inflammatory properties by breaking down heme into biliverdin, carbon monoxide, and iron. By converting hydrogen peroxide into oxygen and water, catalase (CAT) lessens oxidative damage(37).

Biological Effects: Increases Oxidative Stress Resistance in Cells Reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) are neutralized by the overexpression of detoxifying and antioxidant enzymes. Prevents oxidative damage to macromolecules such as proteins, lipids, and DNA. Protection of the heart reduces inflammation and oxidative stress to stop endothelial impairment. Enhances cholesterol outflow and decreases lipid peroxidation to prevent atherosclerosis(38).regulates nitric oxide signaling to maintain blood pressure regulation. Potential Therapeutic

Applications of Neuroprotection in Neurodegenerative diseases neurodegenerative illnesses including Parkinson's disease (PD) and Alzheimer's disease (AD) have been the subject of much research on Nrf2 activation. It slows the progression of Parkinson's disease by shielding dopaminergic neurons from neurotoxins and oxidative stress. Nrf2 preserves cognitive function in Alzheimer's disease by lowering tau protein aggregation, neuroinflammation, and amyloid-beta toxicity(37),(39).

NF- κ B Signaling (Inflammation Reduction):

NF- κ B Signaling and the Reduction of Inflammation. One important modulator of inflammation and immunological response is the Nuclear Factor Kappa B (NF- κ B) signaling pathway. It regulates the expression of several pro-inflammatory genes, such as those that code for cytokines, chemokines, and adhesion molecules. Transient NF- κ B activation is necessary for tissue repair and immune defense, but chronic overactivation is linked to chronic inflammation and a number of illnesses, including inflammation-driven malignancies, atherosclerosis, arthritis, and neuroinflammation(40),(41).

Mechanism of Action: How Quercetin Works as a Natural NF- κ B Inhibitor A common flavonoid in fruits and vegetables, quercetin has been shown to naturally suppress NF- κ B activation. It uses several methods to achieve its anti-inflammatory effects:

I κ B Kinase (IKK) Inhibition: When inflammation is normal, NF- κ B is attached to its inhibitor protein, I κ B α , and stays dormant in the cytoplasm. I κ B α is phosphorylated and then degraded when pro-inflammatory signals like tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) or Toll-like receptors (tlrs) activate

it(42). Because of this breakdown, NF- κ b is free to move into the nucleus and start the transcription of genes that cause inflammation. By inhibiting κ b kinase (IKK), quercetin stops κ b from being phosphorylated and degraded. Consequently, NF- κ b stays trapped in the cytoplasm, which lowers the transcription of genes that promote inflammation(43).

Suppression of NF- κ b activation induced by TNF- α : One important cytokine that promotes the synthesis of inflammatory mediators is TNF- α , which initiates the NF- κ b signaling cascade. By directly blocking TNF- α -induced NF- κ b activation, quercetin lessens the inflammation-causing effects of TNF- α . Toll-Like Receptor (TLR) Activation Modulation(44). Because they can identify damage-associated molecular patterns (damps) and pathogen-associated molecular patterns are essential parts of the innate immune system. When TLR signaling is overactivated, inflammation and increased NF- κ b activity result. Quercetin lowers inflammatory responses by inhibiting TLR-mediated NF- κ b activation(45).

Quercetin's Effect on Biological Process: Quercetin significantly reduces inflammation in a number of medical disorders by altering NF- κ b signaling. Decrease in Pro-Inflammatory Enzymes and Cytokines. The expression of important inflammatory mediators is reduced by quercetin, including enzyme that contributes to the synthesis of pro-inflammatory prostaglandins is cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2)(46).

TNF- α : A cytokine that increases inflammation and encourages the recruitment of immune cells. One of the main pro-inflammatory cytokines linked to fever and immunological reactions is interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β). One cytokine that contributes to autoimmune disorders and

chronic inflammation is interleukin-6 (IL-6)(47).

Reduction of Inflammatory Conditions: By encouraging inflammation in the brain, NF- κ b plays a critical role in neurodegenerative illnesses like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's. By preventing microglial activation and lowering the synthesis of neurotoxic inflammatory mediators, quercetin has been demonstrated to protect neurons(48).

Atherosclerosis: Cardiovascular disorders are caused by atherosclerotic plaques, which are a result of chronic vascular inflammation. Quercetin decreases adhesion molecule production and endothelial cell activation, which in turn limits monocyte penetration into blood arteries(49).

Arthritis: Excessive NF- κ b activation causes synovial inflammation and joint damage in rheumatoid arthritis. By preventing inflammatory cytokines and shielding cartilage from deterioration, quercetin lowers joint inflammation. Possible Effects on Cancer Prevention: One of the main causes of carcinogenesis is chronic inflammation, which encourages tumor growth and spread. NF- κ b activation is frequently seen in a number of malignancies, such as prostate, breast, and colon cancer. Quercetin may aid in halting the development and spread of tumors by lowering NF- κ b-mediated inflammation. Additionally, it protects healthy cells from oxidative stress while promoting apoptosis, or programmed cell death, in cancer cells(50).

3Pi3k/Akt and MAPK Pathways in Cell Survival and Apoptosis:

Intracellular signaling networks closely govern cell survival, growth, and programmed cell death (apoptosis). Among these, the Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase (MAPK) and Phosphoinositide 3-kinase

(PI3K)/Akt pathways are essential for preserving cellular homeostasis, reacting to outside stimuli, and regulating the growth of tumors. These pathways are significantly impacted by quercetin, a flavonoid present in a variety of fruits and vegetables. While shielding healthy cells from excessive apoptosis brought on by oxidative stress and inflammation, it can inhibit the survival and growth of cancer cells(51),(52).

MAPK Pathway Modulation by Quercetin: There are three main sub-pathways in the **C-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK)** Associated with inflammation, apoptosis, and stress reactions. **p38 MAPK** Apoptosis results from the activation of p38 MAPK in response to stimuli such as UV light and cytokines. Extracellular, Cell division and proliferation are controlled by extracellular signal-regulated kinases (ERK1/2)(53),(54).

Quercetin's Impact on the MAPK Pathway:

By inhibiting JNK and p38 MAPK, normal cells are shielded from oxidative stress and stress-induced apoptosis is decreased. **Control of ERK1/2 Activation** → Adjusts cell division and proliferation. Unchecked cell proliferation in cancer is frequently associated with excessive ERK1/2 activation. By inhibiting ERK1/2 hyperactivation in tumor cells, quercetin can stop their uncontrollably rapid growth(55).

Modulation of the PI3K/Akt Pathway by Quercetin: One important pro-survival and anti-apoptotic signaling pathway that is commonly triggered in cancer is the PI3K/Akt pathway. By preventing apoptosis and encouraging cell division, this mechanism aids in cell survival(56). **Quercetin's Impact on the PI3K/Akt Activation Inhibition** quercetin inhibits PI3K/Akt activation in cancer cells, lowering their capacity to endure and divide.

Bcl-2, an anti-apoptotic protein that aids cancer cells in avoiding cell death, is suppressed when anti-apoptotic proteins are downregulated. Pro-apoptotic proteins are upregulated, which activates BAX and other pro-apoptotic factors and causes cancer cells to undergo apoptosis(57),(54).

Biological Effects of Quercetin on Cell Survival and Apoptosis:

Quercetin's biological effects on cell survival and apoptosis and its potential to prevent cancer

causes cancer cells to undergo apoptosis via modifying MAPK pathways and blocking PI3K/Akt. Interferes with survival signals to inhibit the growth of malignant cells. Controls the mechanisms of cellular invasion and migration to prevent metastasis(58). **Safeguarding the Healthiest Cells.** Protects healthy cells against apoptosis brought on by oxidative stress. Lessens cell damage brought on by inflammation. **Cell Cycle Checkpoint Regulation:** Prevents uncontrolled cell division by modulating key checkpoint proteins. Promotes cell cycle arrest in cancer cells, preventing tumor progression(59).

SIRT1 Activation: Its Function in Neuroprotection and Longevity

One important NAD⁺-dependent deacetylase that is essential for controlling cellular metabolism, neuroprotection, and lifespan is sirtuin 1 (SIRT1). It affects a number of biological functions, such as inflammation, mitochondrial function, and stress tolerance. A naturally occurring flavonoid called quercetin increases SIRT1 activity, which has a number of neuroprotective and longevity-promoting benefits(60).

Mechanism of Action:

It has been discovered that quercetin increases SIRT1 expression and activity, which has several downstream effects:

Deacetylation of Key Transcription

Factors: Important transcription factors are deacetylated By eliminating acetyl groups from different transcription factors, SIRT1 modifies their activity and controls gene expression(61).Deacetylation of p53 (Tumor Suppressor Protein 53) decreases its pro-apoptotic activity, limiting excessive neuronal cell death and extending neuronal life. OXO (Forehead Box O Transcription Factors),Reduces oxidative damage by enhancing cellular stress tolerance and controlling the expression of antioxidant genes. By inhibiting pro-inflammatory reactions, NF-by (Nuclear Factor Kappa B), protects neurons and lowers neuroinflammation by suppressing pro-inflammatory reactions(62),(45).Regulation of Microglial Activity and Neuroinflammation is largely caused by the brain's immune cells, or microglia. Chronic inflammation brought on by overactivated microglia can exacerbate neurodegenerative conditions like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's. Quercetin reduces the release of inflammatory cytokines such TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6 by inhibiting excessive microglial activation through SIRT1 activation(63).

Biological effect of SIRT1 Activation by quercetin:

Lowering Oxidative Stress and Improving Mitochondrial Function: By activating PGC-1 α (Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor Gamma Coactivator 1-alpha), SIRT1 promotes mitochondrial biogenesis.

Enhances the antioxidant defenses of cells by upregulating enzymes that lessen damage from free radicals, such as catalase and superoxide dismutase (SOD).increases cellular energy efficiency and longevity by enhancing mitochondrial energy output(56),(64).

Encouragement of Neuronal Survival and Synaptic Plasticity Learning, memory, and brain function all depend on synaptic plasticity. By encouraging the expression of neurotrophic factors such as BDNF (Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor), SIRT1 strengthens synapses(39).shields neurons from the toxicity of amyloid-beta, which is linked to Alzheimer's disease inhibits apoptosis in response to inflammation and oxidative damage, promoting neuronal survival(65).

Improvement of Insulin Sensitivity and

Metabolic Balance: SIRT1 is important for maintaining metabolic homeostasis, and quercetin-mediated SIRT1 activation offers a number of advantage increases insulin sensitivity by activating and deacetylating metabolic regulators that improve glucose metabolism, such as AMPK (AMP-activated protein kinase) and PGC-1 α .improves lipid metabolism and lowers inflammation associated with obesity by controlling genes related to energy expenditure and fat accumulation. Prevents age-related metabolic decline, obesity, and type 2 diabetes, among other metabolic diseases(66),(37).

Quercetin exerts neuroprotective effects through various mechanisms

Antioxidant Activity: Quercetin's antioxidant properties serve a substantial role in minimizing neurodegenerative illnesses by counteracting oxidative stress, which is a significant characteristic in conditions such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, and other neurodegenerative disorders. Here's how quercetin's antioxidant mechanisms specifically relate to neurodegenerative diseases (67,68). In neurodegenerative diseases, various factors such as genetic mutations, environmental toxins, and mitochondrial dysfunction results in an imbalance between the production and

clearance of ROS(69). As a result, there is an excess accumulation of free radicals, including superoxide anion ($O_2^{\bullet-}$), hydroxyl radical ($\bullet OH$), and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), within neuronal cells and surrounding tissues(70). These ROS are highly reactive and can initiate chain reactions that cause oxidative damage to cellular components.(71). ROS-induced oxidative damage is a key factor in the pathophysiology of neurodegenerative disorders. Lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation, and DNA damage may affect cellular function and disturb crucial brain functions including neurotransmitter release, synaptic plasticity, and mitochondrial function(72),(73). Over time, this oxidative stress contributes to the progressive

degeneration of neurons and the development of cognitive, motor, and behavioral deficits characteristic of neurodegenerative disorders.(74). It acts as a scavenger of free radicals, including ROS, by donating hydrogen atoms or electrons to neutralize their reactivity. Its potential to quench reactive radicals and prevent oxidative damage to biomolecules(75). Quercetin's antioxidant activity protects lipids from peroxidation, preserves protein structure and function, and prevents DNA strand breaks and mutations. Quercetin play a role to maintain neuronal integrity, function, and viability of oxidative stress (76), (77).

Chelating Metal Ions: Iron and copper are essential trace metals required for many physiological processes in the brain, including neurotransmitter synthesis, myelin formation, and antioxidant defense(78). Excessive accumulation of these metals, particularly in their free or loosely bound. This accumulation may result from disrupted metal homeostasis, impaired metal transport mechanisms, or environmental exposure to metal pollutants(79). This protective effect helps preserve the integrity of neuronal membranes, maintain protein structure and function, and prevent DNA damage, ultimately promoting neuronal survival and function (80), (81). By targeting the underlying mechanisms of metal-induced oxidative damage, Quercetin could potentially decrease the course of several illnesses and relieve accompanying symptoms (82).

Inducing Antioxidant Enzymes: Quercetin, flavonoid compounds found abundantly in numerous fruits, vegetables, and grains, has garnered more attention for its possible health advantages, notably its antioxidant effects (83). Oxidative stress, which arises from an imbalance between the generation

of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the capacity of antioxidant defense systems to counteract them, is linked to the development of a number of neurodegenerative illnesses as well as cognitive loss inside the brain. Quercetin increases the activity of important antioxidant enzymes to provide neuroprotective effects (84,85). An important antioxidant enzyme called superoxide dismutase catalyzes the transformation of superoxide radicals into hydrogen peroxide and molecular oxygen(86). This reaction is crucial because superoxide radicals are highly reactive molecules that can damage cellular components, including proteins, lipids, and DNA(87).

Anti-inflammatory Effects: Quercetin suppresses inflammatory cytokines, modulates microglial activation, and inhibits nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B) signaling, attenuating neuroinflammation(88). Quercetin exhibits several anti-inflammatory mechanisms of action that are relevant to mitigating neurodegenerative diseases(89). Here's how quercetin's anti-inflammatory properties can impact neurodegenerative conditions:

Inhibition of Pro-inflammatory Mediators: Neuroinflammation leads to the activation of resident immune cells, such as microglia and astrocytes, leading to the production and release of pro-inflammatory mediators including cytokines TNF- α , interleukins, chemokines, and prostaglandins(89,90).

Modulation of Inflammatory Markers: The nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B) signaling pathway is one ways quercetins decrease inflammation. The transcription factor NF- κ B plays a crucial role in controlling the expression of genes linked to

immune responses and inflammation(74,91). Quercetin inhibits NF- κ B activation through restricting its translocation to the nucleus and subsequent binding to DNA. This suppresses the transcription of pro-inflammatory genes, including those encoding cytokines like TNF- α and iNOS. Quercetin inhibits NF- κ B activation, reducing pro-inflammatory cytokine production and neuroinflammatory reactions in the brain(92,93). Quercetin can modulate other signaling pathways implicated in inflammation, such as mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs) and signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (STAT3)(94). Quercetin restricts the activation of MAPKs, thereby attenuating the generation of pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines. Additionally, quercetin suppresses STAT-3 activation(95). Which is associated with the regulation of inflammatory gene expression. By targeting multiple signaling pathways, quercetin exerts broad anti-inflammatory effects, reducing the levels of pro-inflammatory mediators in the brain(96).

Suppression of Microglial Activation: Dysregulation of microglial activity may lead to excessive activation and the generation of pro-inflammatory cytokines and reactive oxygen species (ROS), which contributes to neuronal injury and accelerates disease development.(97). Quercetin, a natural flavonoid with potent anti-inflammatory properties, has been demonstrated to modulate microglial activation and attenuate neuroinflammation, thereby protecting neurons from inflammatory damage(98). Microglial activation is a hallmark feature of neuroinflammation in various neurodegenerative disorders, including Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, and multiple sclerosis. Activated microglia can adopt different phenotypes, including pro-

inflammatory (M1) and anti-inflammatory (M2) states(99). In pathological conditions, such as neurodegenerative diseases, microglia often shift towards the pro-inflammatory M1 phenotype, releasing cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β), and interleukin-6 (IL-6), as well as ROS and other cytotoxic molecules(100).

Quercetin has been shown to suppress microglial activation and shift the microglial phenotype towards the anti-inflammatory M2 state. Quercetin attenuates neuroinflammatory responses by preventing microglia from activating and therefore reducing the release and synthesis of pro-inflammatory cytokines and ROS(101). Quercetin inhibits NF- κ B signaling, MAPK pathways, and regulates the activity of inflammatory enzymes, among other methods, to provide its anti-inflammatory properties (102).

Quercetin can modulate MAPK pathways, ERK, JNK, and p38 MAPK, which associated with microglial activation and inflammatory responses. By inhibiting MAPK activation, quercetin suppresses the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and ROS in activated microglia(103).

Enhancement of Anti-inflammatory Pathways: Quercetin possesses the remarkable ability to enhance the activity of anti-inflammatory pathways within the brain, thereby playing a crucial role in mitigating neuroinflammation associated with neurodegenerative diseases. One important way through which quercetin reduces inflammation is by encouraging the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin-10 (IL-10)(104,105).

IL-10 belongs to class of an anti-inflammatory cytokine & known for its ability to suppress inflammatory responses and promote tissue repair. It acts by inhibiting the generation of pro-

inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6, and by modulating the activity of immune cells involved in inflammation, including macrophages and T cells. IL-10 exerts its protective effects by dampening excessive inflammation and facilitating the resolution of inflammatory processes, thereby preventing tissue damage and promoting healing(106),(107).

In vitro and in vivo studies have shown that quercetin increases the expression of IL-10 in a variety of cell types, including immune cells and neurons (108). Through its molecular interactions, quercetin promotes the transcription and translation of IL-10, leading to increased levels of this anti-inflammatory cytokine within the brain. By enhancing IL-10 production, quercetin effectively amplifies the anti-inflammatory signaling cascades, promoting a shift towards a more balanced and controlled inflammatory response (109),(110).

Enhancement of Protein Degradation:

Quercetin enhance protein degradation pathways within cells. Two primary pathways linked with the clearance of misfolded and aggregated proteins from cells are the ubiquitin-proteasome system and the autophagy-lysosome pathway(111). Quercetin modulate these pathways, leading to the efficient removal of misfolded protein aggregates and thereby mitigating neurodegeneration(112). A tightly controlled cellular mechanism called the ubiquitin-proteasome system is in charge of the targeted breakdown of misfolded and short-lived proteins (113,114). Central to this process is the tagging of target proteins with ubiquitin molecules, marking them for proteasomal degradation. Quercetin has been demonstrated to enhance the activity of the UPS by various mechanisms(115,116). It is capable of interacting directly with UPS equipment components, such as ubiquitin ligases, thereby facilitating the

ubiquitination of target proteins. Quercetin possesses antioxidant properties, which can alleviate oxidative stress-induced inhibition of the UPS, thereby promoting protein degradation(117,118). The autophagy-lysosome pathway is another essential mechanism for the recycling and autolysis of cellular component, including misfolded proteins and damaged organelles. Cytoplasmic cargo is taken up by autophagosomes during autophagy and transported to lysosomes for destruction(119),(120). Quercetin has been shown to induce autophagy through multiple pathways. It has the ability to trigger the development of autophagosomes by activating important autophagy regulators including AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) and mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR). (121,122). Moreover, quercetin can modulate the expression and activity of various autophagy-related genes and proteins, thereby enhancing the overall autophagic flux(123). By promoting the activity of both the UPS and autophagy-lysosome pathway, quercetin facilitates the clearance of toxic protein aggregates from cells. These aggregates, which are often associated with neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease, can impair cellular function and viability through mechanisms such as proteotoxicity, oxidative stress, and inflammation(124),(125).

Stabilization of Protein Structure:

This stabilization involves quercetin's interaction with hydrophobic regions of proteins, a process that have profound for preventing protein misfolding and aggregation(126). Proteins of biological systems, rely on specific three-dimensional structures to perform their functions effectively. Various factors, such as environmental stressors or genetic mutations can disrupt structures (127). Misfolded proteins not only

functionally impaired but also prone to forming aggregates, It can be toxic to cells and etiology of a number of illnesses,as neurological disease like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's (128,129). By binding hydrophobic patches, quercetin effectively "shields" from interacting with proteins or forming same protein molecule(130),(131).

neurogenesis, enhances synaptic plasticity, and inhibits neuronal apoptosis, neuronal survival and regeneration in neurodegenerative disease (132). It exhibits many mode of action that enhancement of neuronal survival and regeneration, which are essential for combating neurodegenerative diseases(133). Here's an outline of these mechanisms:

Enhancement of Neuronal Survival and Regeneration: Quercetin promotes

Neuroprotection Against Oxidative Stress: Quercetin has a potent antioxidant properties that protect neurons against oxidative stress (134). By decreasing oxidative damage and scavenging free radicals to neuronal cells, quercetin supports neuronal survival and prevents from degeneration(135).

Promotion of Neurogenesis: Quercetin has been promote neurogenesis, the neural stem cells or progenitor cells in the brain produce new neurons (136). By elevate neurogenesis, quercetin supports the growth and development of neurons, It is critical for repairing damaged neuronal circuits and repair neurons in neurodegenerative diseases(137).

Induction of Neurotrophic Factors:

Neurotrophic factors including nerve growth factor (NGF) and brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) may be expressed when quercetin is present(138), which are essential for the survival of neurons, growth, and differentiation. By increasing the levels of neurotrophic factors, quercetin promotes neuronal survival and supports the regeneration of damaged neurons in neurodegenerative conditions(139),(140).

Modulation of Signaling Pathways:

Quercetin modulates various signaling pathways linked with neuronal survival, regeneration, and synaptic plasticity. For example, it can activate the PI3K/Akt

pathway, which promotes cell survival and growth, and the ERK pathway(141,142) which is involved in neuronal differentiation and regeneration. By modulating these signaling pathways, quercetin enhances neuronal resilience and facilitates the regeneration of damaged neuronal networks(141),(140).

Regulation of Neurotransmitter Levels:

Quercetin modulates neurotransmitter systems, including dopaminergic, cholinergic, and glutamatergic pathways, influencing synaptic transmission and neuronal excitability (143).

Here's an overview of the mechanisms quercetin influences neurotransmitter levels:

Modulation of Dopamine and Serotonin:

Quercetin affects the brain's levels of neurotransmitters including serotonin and dopamine[163]. There is a high level of dopamine and serotonin abnormalities in neurodegenerative disease (144). Quercetin enhance the synthesis and release of dopamine and serotonin, promoting

neurotransmitter balance and improving neuronal degeneration(145).

CONCLUSION

Neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Huntington's disease, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. It defined by ongoing loss

of neurons, oxidative stress, long-term inflammation in the brain, protein misfolding, and imbalances in neurotransmitters. Neurodegenerative diseases have many causes, need treatment strategies address multiple harmful. Quercetin is a naturally flavonoid found in fruits and vegetables. It shows little promise for protecting the brain due to it varies biological effects. Quercetin antioxidant properties help neutralize reactive oxygen species, bind to metals, and improve the body's own antioxidant defenses. Additionally, it disrupts harmful protein buildup, boosts protein removal through autophagy and the ubiquitin-proteasome system, increases neurotrophic factors, supports the growth of new neurons, regulates neurotransmitter systems, and shields neurons from damage caused by excessive stimulation. While many in vitro and in vivo studies support quercetin's protective effects on the brain, there is limited clinical evidence. Issues like low bioavailability, quick metabolism, and a lack of large-scale human trials need to be resolved to make its therapeutic use viable. In summary, quercetin is a promising natural compound with potential uses in preventing and treating neurodegenerative diseases. More research is needed on effective delivery methods, improving how the body processes it, and well-structured clinical trials to confirm its usefulness and develop evidence-based guidelines for its use in brain protection.

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